

A STUDY ON STRATEGIES TO HANDLE MENTAL DISORDERS AFFECTING PRODUCTIVITY AT WORKPLACE

Dr. Shobha Bennet Mathew

M.Com, MPhil, SET, MBA, MA - Clinical Psychology, PhD

K. J. Somaiya College of Arts and Commerce, Mumbai University

Mob- 98333282988, Email- shobha.mathew@somaiya .edu

Paper Received On: 20 NOVEMBER 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 DECEMBER 2025

Published On: 01 JANUARY 2026

Introduction

A mental disorder is characterized by a clinically significant disturbance in an individual's cognition, emotional regulation, or behavior. It is usually associated with distress or impairment in important areas of functioning. There are many different types of mental disorders. Mental disorders may also be referred to as mental health conditions. The latter is a broader term covering mental disorders, psychosocial disabilities and (other) mental states associated with significant distress, impairment in functioning, or risk of self-harm. This fact sheet focuses on mental disorders as described by the International Classification of Diseases 11th Revision (ICD-11).

According to WHO

- 1 in every 8 people in the world live with a mental disorder
- Mental disorders involve significant disturbances in thinking, emotional regulation, or behaviour
- There are many different types of mental disorders
- Effective prevention and treatment options exist
- Most people do not have access to effective care

Work overload can contribute to mental health problems such as burnout, anxiety, and depression. Symptoms may include emotional exhaustion, decreased performance, mood

changes, sleep disturbances, and physical issues like headaches or a weakened immune system.

Objective of the study

To understand the most common type of mental disorder in organizations

To analyze the causes of mental disorder in organizations

To bring out the best solutions for reducing mental disorder at work place.

Research Methodology

A sample of 32 people participated in the survey.

Data Analysis

Are you working ?
32 responses

96.9% of the respondents were working.

Does mental disorder affect productivity in organisation?
32 responses

93.9% of the respondents felt that it affects productivity in the organization. This indicates that mental health of an employee is very important for the productivity of an organization.

Which mental disorder have you seen commonly in work environments?

32 responses

68.8% of the respondents felt that depression is the most common mental disorder found in organizations.

46.9% of the respondents felt that Generalized anxiety disorder is most common mental disorder found in organizations.

40.6% of the respondents felt that panic disorder is most common mental disorder found in organizations.

37.5% of the respondents felt that social anxiety disorder is most common mental disorder found in organizations.

This indicates that depression, generalized anxiety disorder, panic attacks and social anxiety are the most common disorders found in organisations.

What are the common causes of mental disorder in workplace?

32 responses

68.8% of the respondents feels work overload is the main cause for mental disorders in organization.

40.6% of the respondents feels groupism is the main cause for mental disorders in organization.
37.5% of the respondents feels poor personal relationships is the main cause for mental disorders in organization.

37.5% of the respondents feels lack of resources is the main cause for mental disorders in organization.

The above analyzes indicates that work overload, groupism, poor personal relationships and lack of resources are the major causes of mental disorders in organisations.

Do you think unconditional positive strokes is important while handling an employee with mental disorder?
32 responses

71.9% of the respondents feel that unconditional positive strokes should be given to an employee suffering from mental disorder in organization.

Do you think in work environment coworkers provide unconditional positive strokes to an employee with mental disorder?
32 responses

37.5% of the respondents felt that coworkers provide unconditional positive strokes in an organization.

34.4% of the respondents felt that coworkers might be providing unconditional positive strokes in an organization.

28.1% of the respondents felt that coworkers do not provide unconditional positive strokes in an organization.

Does your organization have Employee Assistance Programs?
32 responses

65.5% of the employees said their organization does not have an Employee Assistance Programs.

34.4% employees said their organization have Employee Assistance Programs in their organization.

This indicates that there is lack of facilities to tackle mental disorders in majority of organizations.

Do you think employees of an organization should be trained to handle cases of mental disorders empathically?
32 responses

93.8% of the respondents felt that an organization should train employees to handle cases of mental disorder.

Do you think work life balance can improve the mental health of employees in the organization?

32 responses

84.4% of the respondents felt that work life balance can improve mental health of employees in organizations.

Conclusions:

93.9% of the respondents felt that it affects productivity in the organization. This indicates that mental health of an employee is very important for the productivity of an organization.

68.8% of the respondents felt that depression is the most common mental disorder found in organizations.

46.9% of the respondents felt that Generalized anxiety disorder is most common mental disorder found in organizations.

40.6% of the respondents felt that panic disorder is most common mental disorder found in organizations.

37.5% of the respondents felt that social anxiety disorder is most common mental disorder found in organizations.

68.8% of the respondents feels work overload is the main cause for mental disorders in organization.

40.6% of the respondents feels groupism is the main cause for mental disorders in organization.

37.5% of the respondents feels poor personal relationships is the main cause for mental disorders in organization.

37.5% of the respondents feels lack of resources is the main cause for mental disorders in organization.

65.5% of the employees said their organization does not have an Employee Assistance Programs.

34.4% employees said their organization have Employee Assistance Programs in their organization.

This indicates that there is lack of facilities to tackle mental disorders in majority of organizations.

93.8% of the respondents felt that an organization should train employees to handle cases of mental disorder.

37.5% of the respondents felt that coworkers provide unconditional positive strokes in an organization.

34.4% of the respondents felt that coworkers might be providing unconditional positive strokes in an organization.

28.1% of the respondents felt that coworkers do not provide unconditional positive strokes in an organization.

Suggestions to handle mental health /mental disorders in organizations:

The following are the suggestion given by respondents to improve mental health of their employee's in organizations or the following strategies can be followed by organizations to tackle mental disorders in organizations which will in turn improve productivity :

Make psychiatric help available.

The organization should conduct seminars for work life balance, Counselling session, regular feedback and follow-up meeting,

Better work life balance would help

Show empathy, create awareness around specific mental health conditions like depression, have dedicated Employee Assistance Programs and proper grievance redressal system so employees feel heard.

Be more empathetic towards them and help them deal with their disorders through counselling etc.

Being professional, being planned and not disturbing employees after working hours

Hold seminars to improve the morale of the workforce

Psycho educate the workers

Be considerate, conducting Meditation, staff picnic, colleague co-operation, medical check - up, training from time to time. My org is already doing wellbeing at work program and also arrange timely sessions for all employees on yoga, meditation and other activities that keeps individual at peace

Avoid overburden on staff

Give less pressure, conduct meditation, create conducive environment, ensure growth and stability, treat employees with respect and dignity

Keep happy and positive work environment without comparing and pressurizing employees at work place

Employee centered policies should be made.

Accountability of work required at work place.

People who need support should ask for a temporary relief else it puts a lot of burden on others.

Maintain perfect shift timings and does not extend logout times

Do a psychiatrist evaluation yearly

More socializing, sharing & caring by superiors and colleagues, setting realistic targets, mandatory physical exercises and yoga sessions for all and make it part of duty, say for 10 mts. everyday.

Sensitize all employee to show empathy towards mental disorder person.

Have mental health trainings

Check the work pressure, have certain kind of re creational activity in office like a yoga or hobby activity or sessions

References

"Office of the NIMH Director". *National Institute of Mental Health*. 31 July 2024.

"NIMH Directors". *NIH*. June 20, 2024.

"National Institute of Mental Health: Important Events in NIMH History". Archived from the original on 2007-03-10.

"National Institute of Mental Health". *NIH Almanac*. 2017.

"About NIMH". *National Institute of Mental Health*. Retrieved 21 May 2013.

"The National Institute of Mental Health Strategic Plan". *National Institute of Mental Health (United States)*. Retrieved 21 May 2013.

"NIMH » The National Institute of Mental Health Strategic Plan". *www.nimh.nih.gov*. 24 May 2024.

"Records of the Alcohol, Drug Abuse, and Mental Health Administration [ADAMHA] (Record Group 511), 1929-93". *National Archives. U.S. National Archives and Records Administration*. Retrieved 18 July 2012.

<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-disorders>

Robbins, S. P. (2009). *Organizational behaviour*. Cape Town, Pearson.